

KNOWLEDGE GAINS: SUMMARY AND IMPLICATION REPORT 1

MARCH 2020

IMPROVED CHARACTERIZATION AND UNDERSTANDING OF THE ERF CONCEPT

Authors: Gunnar Myhre¹ and Johannes Quaas². Review Editors: Tim Andrews³ and Jim Haywood³

¹CICERO Oslo, Norway; ²University of Leipzig, Germany; ³Met Office, UK

KEY MESSAGES

- This KGSIR summarizes recent advances in our understanding of Effective Radiative Forcing (ERF), and methods to quantify ERF.
- ERF is better constrained by using key observations of changes to the climate system in recent advances.
- Uncertainties in ERF due to changes in CO₂ and other climate forcings remain substantial.
- Knowledge gains have been achieved on comparing various climate drivers relative to CO₂ changes.
- Next steps are to quantify causes of the diversity in ERF due to CO₂ in climate models, and improve understanding of aerosol-cloud interactions and thereby their ERF.

CONTEXT

Effective radiative forcing (ERF) is a perturbation to the Earth's energy budget by a climate driver, such as a change in atmospheric concentrations of greenhouse gases or aerosols. ERF is quantified at the top of the atmosphere and is essential to climate science since a change in the Earth's energy budget also leads to a surface temperature change.

ERF has been defined to include a) the initial radiative perturbation to the climate system (such as a reduction in outgoing radiation to space after an increase in greenhouse gases), and b) changes in the atmosphere occurring before global mean surface temperature changes (such as aerosol-cloud interactions and changes to atmospheric temperature). This allows a better representation of surface temperature change between climate drivers (Boucher et al., 2013; Myhre et al., 2013). The atmospheric changes occurring on a short time scale, after the initial radiative perturbation by the climate driver, are known as rapid adjustments (Quaas and Myhre, 2020).

Uncertainties in anthropogenically induced ERF are substantial where atmospheric aerosols are the main driver. The causes of the uncertainties are also different for atmospheric aerosols and greenhouse gases.

For aerosols, a strong regional and temporal variation in concentration combined with lack of a complete process understanding are major causes of uncertainty. Greenhouse gases are to a large extent well-mixed in the atmosphere and the physical understanding of their initial radiative perturbation to the energy budget is mostly well known. Nevertheless, simulations of greenhouse gases in global climate models are associated with uncertainties in ERF because of approximations in radiative transfer scheme, and rapid atmospheric adjustments from the initial perturbation.

SUMMARY OF KNOWLEDGE GAINS

UNCERTAINTIES IN TOTAL EFFECTIVE RADIATIVE FORCING

Figure 1 shows the probability distribution function (PDF) of ERF based on estimates of the Earth's radiative response combined with historical observations of changes in global mean temperature and the Earth's total heat uptake (Andrews and Forster, 2020).

The uncertainty ranges based on the PDF are compared to the IPCC Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) (Myhre et al., 2013) and the Fifth Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5) simulations (Taylor et al., 2012). In addition to the total ERF from all anthropogenic climate drivers, the PDF of ERF from atmospheric aerosols are also shown. The time periods in the three estimates are approximately the same (from pre-industrial to around 2010).

In Figure 1 the estimate for total ERF is $+2.3$ [$+1.7$ to $+3.0$] W m^{-2} (5-95% confidence interval) which is a reduction in the uncertainty range of 40% compared to the estimate from IPCC AR5. Figure 1 also shows a similar best estimate

and uncertainty range for total aerosols ERF estimated in Andrews and Forster (2020) and IPCC AR5. The results shown in Figure 1 suggest that many global climate models from CMIP5 may include a cooling effect from anthropogenic aerosols that is too strong.

EFFECTIVE RADIATIVE FORCING DUE TO CO₂ CHANGES

Uncertainties in the radiative forcing of CO₂ changes in Global Climate Models (GCMs) have been a long-standing problem (Cess et al., 1993; Collins et al., 2006; Soden et al., 2018). Between the most accurate radiative transfer schemes available (line-by-line), the differences in forcing due to CO₂ changes are small (Soden et al., 2018) and it is a similar case for the uncertainties associated with the spectroscopic data (Mlynarczyk et al., 2016). However, in GCMs the radiative transfer schemes need to be simplified because of computer time requirements, which causes differences due to uncertainties in the applied parameterizations.

FIGURE 1: Historical ERF derived from an energy budget constraint. The black line shows historical ERF (1861–1880 to near-present) probability distribution function derived from historical energy budget constraints (Andrews and Forster, 2020). The blue line denotes the aerosol component. The 5-95% uncertainty range of historical ERF as assessed by IPCC AR5 is shown in red and the one inferred from the Fifth Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5) climate model ERFs in grey. Grey dots represent individual CMIP5 models. Lines and bars represent the best estimate and 5-95% confidence interval.

Figure 2a shows multi-model simulations of ERF from the Precipitation Driver Response Model Intercomparison Project (PDRMIP) (Myhre et al., 2017) and the Radiative Forcing Model Intercomparison Project (RFMIP) (Pincus et al., 2016) for a doubling in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. The RFMIP results are shown as half of quadrupling of the CO₂ concentrations simulations. The range in PDRMIP and in RFMIP is about 1 W m⁻², with standard deviations of 37 % and 25 %, respectively. Zelinka et al. (2020) found the standard deviation in doubling of atmospheric CO₂ concentration to be reduced by about 30% between GCMs in the newer generation models in the Sixth Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6; here the RFMIP contribution to it) compared to CMIP5 (Soden et al., 2018).

The explanation for the differences in the range in the ERF due to CO₂ in PDRMIP (and CMIP5) compared

to RFMIP is unresolved, but can be due to updates in radiation schemes in the climate models, differences in simulated atmospheric temperature profiles, differences in simulated water vapour which has a strong absorption overlap with CO₂, representation of clouds, or differences in simulated rapid adjustments. Stratospheric cooling due to CO₂ is a well-known feature, and has a large radiative effect for CO₂ changes.

Cloud changes are another important rapid adjustment in the atmosphere, and show large model diversity (Smith et al., 2018). Ongoing work in the CONSTRAIN project is investigating whether there is a particular cause for this diversity or whether it is a combination of several factors. Initial work indicates that temperature differences in the stratosphere may play an important role.

FIGURE 2: Effective Radiative Forcing (W m⁻²) due to a doubling of the CO₂ concentration (a). Green bars are results from PDRMIP and blue bars from RFMIP (taken as half of the quadrupling experiment). Efficacy of a range of climate drivers (b), defined as global, annual mean surface temperature change in response to the ERF in comparison to the surface temperature change in response to the same global-mean ERF due to CO₂ concentration change.

EFFICACY

To understand the role of non-CO₂ climate drivers in past and future evolutions of ERF, the methodology used to quantify ERF is important. Additionally, this has implications for policy decisions since climate metrics (such as global warming potentials - GWP) are applied to compare emissions of non-CO₂ gases relative to CO₂ emissions (Myhre et al., 2013). IPCC AR5 included rapid adjustments beyond stratospheric temperature adjustment to allow a better comparison between climate drivers (Boucher et al., 2013; Myhre et al., 2013). ERF is a useful quantity if the temperature change from a given ERF due to a climate driver (climate sensitivity parameter) is equal to the change in response to a CO₂ ERF of the same magnitude. Therefore, the method to derive the efficacy (ratio of the climate sensitivity parameter for a non-CO₂ climate driver to the climate sensitivity parameter for CO₂) is sought to be as close as possible to 1.0 for all climate drivers.

In PDRMIP the required simulations to quantify efficacy, i.e. simulations to diagnose both ERF and surface temperature change, are available. Figure 2b is obtained thanks to significant contributions from the CONSTRAIN project and shows results for the efficacy for a range of climate drivers as well as some regional experiments (Richardson et al., 2019). Results show an efficacy close to unity, but slightly below for all but one forcing scenario. Richardson et al. (2019) show that the efficacy is even closer to one when the radiative effect of the small land surface temperature change has been corrected in the fixed sea-surface simulation to calculate ERF. The recommended method for calculating ERF in Richardson et al. (2019) has been compared to other approaches.

Overall, knowledge gains from the CONSTRAIN project provide a method to calculate ERF from climate model simulations keeping sea-surface temperature constant. This can be applied to a large range of climate drivers and is thus important for understanding climate change.

ERF OF AEROSOLS

Figure 1 shows the large uncertainty in ERF of anthropogenic aerosols. Aerosols scatter and absorb solar radiation (aerosol-radiation interactions, or direct aerosol effect) and can influence cloud microphysics (aerosol-cloud interactions, or indirect aerosol effect). Bellouin et al. (2020) recently concluded that the radiative effect of anthropogenic aerosols in clear sky is relatively well constrained among several studies including multi-model analysis. Based on this finding Bellouin et al. (2020) estimated a reduction in the uncertainty of the radiative forcing of the direct aerosol effect compared to earlier estimates.

Anthropogenic aerosols increase the number concentration of cloud droplets giving a cooling effect. Compared to other indirect aerosol effects, this effect is relatively well constrained (Ghan et al., 2016; Malavelle et al., 2017)

Recent observation-based studies show that changes to cloud liquid water by anthropogenic aerosols are likely to be small and negative (Malavelle et al., 2017; Toll et al., 2017; Toll et al., 2019). The adjustment of cloud fraction is less well understood (Quaas and Myhre, 2020). The understating of rapid adjustment to aerosol-radiation interactions due to black carbon has been substantially improved, giving a general strong reduction in ERF compared to its direct aerosol effect (Smith et al., 2018).

Overall, there has been progress in the scientific knowledge of the anthropogenic aerosol influences on climate, but only a small reduction in the uncertainty in aerosol ERF (see Figure 1 and further discussion in Bellouin et al. (2020)).

IMPLICATIONS

- A method providing efficacy for a broad range of climate forcers yields values close to unity, which allows improved understanding of the role of non-CO₂ climate drivers on past and future climate change.
- Global Warming Potentials (GWP) or other climate metrics are used in policy decisions on reductions of non-CO₂ gases relative to CO₂ emissions. These are applied in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change and are thus relevant to the Paris agreement. GWPs depend on both ERF and the lifetime of the non-CO₂ greenhouse gases. Improved quantification of ERF, and improved comparability of climate effects of different drivers, implies improved climate metrics.

REFERENCES

- Andrews, T. and Forster, P. M.: Energy budget constraints on historical radiative forcing, *Nature Climate Change*, 2020.
- Bellouin, N., Quaas, J., Gryspeerdt, E., Kinne, S., Stier, P., Watson-Parris, D., Boucher, O., Carslaw, K. S., Christensen, M., Daniau, A.-L., Dufresne, J.-L., Feingold, G., Fiedler, S., Forster, P., Gettelman, A., Haywood, J. M., Lohmann, U., Malavelle, F., Mauritsen, T., McCoy, D. T., Myhre, G., Mülmenstädt, J., Neubauer, D., Possner, A., Rugenstein, M., Sato, Y., Schulz, M., Schwartz, S. E., Sourdeval, O., Storelvmo, T., Toll, V., Winker, D. and Stevens, B.: Bounding Global Aerosol Radiative Forcing of Climate Change, *Reviews of Geophysics*, 58(1), e2019RG000660, 2020.
- Boucher, O., Randall, D., Artaxo, P., Bretherton, C., Feingold, G., Forster, P., Kerminen, V.-M., Kondo, Y., Liao, H., Lohmann, U., Rasch, P., Sathesh, S. K., Sherwood, S., Stevens, B. and Zhang, X.-Y.: Clouds and Aerosols. In: *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. T. F. Stocker, D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S. K. Allen et al. (Editors), Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 571-657, 2013.
- Cess, R. D., Zhang, M.-H., Potter, G. L., Barker, H. W., Colman, R. A., Dazlich, D. A., Del Genio, A. D., Esch, M., Fraser, J. R., Galin, V., Gates, W. L., Hack, J. J., Ingram, W. J., Kiehl, J. T., Lacis, A. A., Le Treut, H., Li, Z.-X., Liang, X.-Z., Mahfouf, J.-F., McAvaney, B. J., Meleshko, V. P., Morcrette, J.-J., Randall, D. A., Roeckner, E., Royer, J.-F., Sokolov, A. P., Sporyshev, P. V., Taylor, K. E., Wang, W.-C. and Wetherald, R. T.: Uncertainties in Carbon Dioxide Radiative Forcing in Atmospheric General Circulation Models, *Science*, 262(5137), 1252-1255, 1993.
- Collins, W. D., Ramaswamy, V., Schwarzkopf, M. D., Sun, Y., Portmann, R. W., Fu, Q., Casa-nova, S. E. B., Dufresne, J. L., Fillmore, D. W., Forster, P. M. D., Galin, V. Y., Gohar, L. K., Ingram, W. J., Kratz, D. P., Lefebvre, M. P., Li, J., Marquet, P., Oinas, V., Tsushima, Y., Uchiyama, T. and Zhong, W. Y.: Radiative forcing by well-mixed greenhouse gases: Estimates from climate models in the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Fourth Assessment Report (AR4), *Journal of Geophysical Research-Atmospheres*, 111(D14), D14317, 2006.
- Ghan, S., Wang, M., Zhang, S., Ferrachat, S., Gettelman, A., Griesfeller, J., Kipling, Z., Lohmann, U., Morrison, H., Neubauer, D., Partridge, D. G., Stier, P., Takemura, T., Wang, H. and Zhang, K.: Challenges in constraining anthropogenic aerosol effects on cloud radiative forcing using present-day spatiotemporal variability, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 113(21), 5804-5811, 2016.
- Malavelle, F. F., Haywood, J. M., Jones, A., Gettelman, A., Clarisse, L., Bauduin, S., Allan, R. P., Karset, I. H. H., Kristjánsson, J. E., Oreopoulos, L., Cho, N., Lee, D., Bellouin, N., Boucher, O., Grosvenor, D. P., Carslaw, K. S., Dhomse, S., Mann, G. W., Schmidt, A., Coe, H., Hartley, M. E., Dalvi, M., Hill, A. A., Johnson, B. T., Johnson, C. E., Knight, J. R., O'Connor, F. M., Partridge, D. G., Stier, P., Myhre, G., Platnick, S., Stephens, G. L., Takahashi, H. and Thordarson, T.: Strong constraints on aerosol-cloud interactions from volcanic eruptions, *Nature*, 546(7659), 485-491, 2017.
- Mlynczak, M. G., Daniels, T. S., Kratz, D. P., Feldman, D. R., Collins, W. D., Mlawer, E. J., Al-varado, M. J., Lawler, J. E., Anderson, L. W., Fahey, D. W., Hunt, L. A. and Mast, J. C.: The spectroscopic foundation of radiative forcing of climate by carbon dioxide, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 43(10), 5318-5325, 2016.
- Myhre, G., Forster, P. M., Samset, B. H., Hodnebrog, Ø., Sillmann, J., Aalbergstjø, S. G., Andrews, T., Boucher, O., Faluvegi, G., Fläschner, D., Iversen, T., Kasoar, M., Kharin, V., Kirkevåg, A., Lamarque, J.-F., Olivé, D., Richardson, T. B., Shindell, D., Shine, K. P., Stjern, C. W., Takemura, T., Voulgarakis, A. and Zwiers, F.: PDRMIP: A Precipitation Driver and Response Model Intercomparison Project—Protocol and Preliminary Results, *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 98(6), 1185-1198, 2017.
- Myhre, G., Shindell, D., Bréon, F.-M., Collins, W., Fuglestedt, J., Huang, J., Koch, D., La-marque, J.-F., Lee, D., Mendoza, B., Nakajima, T., Robock, A., Stephens, G., Takemura, T. and Zhang, H.: Anthropogenic and Natural Radiative Forcing. In: *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. T. F. Stocker, D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S. K. Allen et al. (Editors), Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 659-740, 2013.
- Smith, C. J., Kramer, R. J., Myhre, G., Forster, P. M., Soden, B. J., Andrews, T., et al. (2018). Understanding rapid adjustments to diverse forcing agents. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 45, 12,023-12,031. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GL079826>
- Pincus, R., Forster, P. M. and Stevens, B.: The Radiative Forcing Model Intercomparison Project (RFMIP): experimental protocol for CMIP6, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 9, 3447-3460, 2016.
- Quaas, J., and G. Myhre (2020). State-of-the-art understanding of rapid adjustments. Knowledge Gains: Summary and Implication Report 1. The CONSTRAIN Project, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3711986
- Richardson, T. B., Forster, P. M., Smith, C. J., Maycock, A. C., Wood, T., Andrews, T., Boucher, O., Faluvegi, G., Fläschner, D., Hodnebrog, Ø., Kasoar, M., Kirkevåg, A., Lamarque, J.-F., Mülmenstädt, J., Myhre, G., Olivé, D., Portmann, R. W., Samset, B. H., Shawki, D., Shindell, D., Stier, P., Takemura, T., Voulgarakis, A. and Watson-Parris, D.: Efficacy of Climate Forcings in PDRMIP Models, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 124(23), 12824-12844, 2019.
- Smith, C. J., Kramer, R. J., Myhre, G., Forster, P. M., Soden, B. J., Andrews, T., Boucher, O., Faluvegi, G., Fläschner, D., Hodnebrog, Ø., Kasoar, M., Kharin, V., Kirkevåg, A., La-marque, J.-F., Mülmenstädt, J., Olivé, D., Richardson, T., Samset, B. H., Shindell, D., Stier, P., Takemura, T., Voulgarakis, A. and Watson-Parris, D.: Understanding Rapid Adjustments to Diverse Forcing Agents, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 45(21), 12,023-12,031, 2018.
- Soden, B. J., Collins, W. D. and Feldman, D. R.: Reducing uncertainties in climate models, *Science*, 361(6400), 326-327, 2018.
- Taylor, K. E., Stouffer, R. J. and Meehl, G. A.: An Overview of CMIP5 and the Experiment Design, *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 93(4), 485-498, 2012.
- Toll, V., Christensen, M., Gassó, S. and Bellouin, N.: Volcano and Ship Tracks Indicate Excessive Aerosol-Induced Cloud Water Increases in a Climate Model, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 44(24), 12,492-12,500, 2017.
- Toll, V., Christensen, M., Quaas, J. and Bellouin, N.: Weak average liquid-cloud-water response to anthropogenic aerosols, *Nature*, 572(7767), 51-55, 2019.
- Zelinka, M. D., Myers, T. A., McCoy, D. T., Po-Chedley, S., Caldwell, P. M., Ceppi, P., Klein, S. A. and Taylor, K. E.: Causes of Higher Climate Sensitivity in CMIP6 Models, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 47(1), e2019GL085782, 2020.

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Gunnar Myhre is co-lead for CONSTRAIN Work Package 1 “Effective radiative forcing and rapid adjustments”. He is Research Director at CICERO, leads the international Precipitation and Driver Response Model Intercomparison Project (PDRMIP), and is part of the steering committee of the two CMIP6 endorsed MIPs: RFMIP and AerChemMIP. He was a Lead Author for the IPCC third and fourth assessment reports and a Coordinating Lead Author for the fifth assessment report (AR5).

Johannes Quaas also co-leads CONSTRAIN Work Package 1. He is Professor for Theoretical Meteorology at the University of Leipzig. His research interest is in clouds and climate change, in particular aerosol-cloud interactions, analysis of satellite observations, and atmospheric modelling. Johannes is lead author for the IPCC 6th Assessment Report Working Group I.

ABOUT THIS KNOWLEDGE GAINS: SUMMARY AND IMPLICATION REPORT

CONSTRAIN’s Knowledge Gains: Summary and Implication Reports outline CONSTRAIN’s contributions to the peer reviewed literature (knowledge gains), and summarise the implications for both the scientific community and broader society. This report and other CONSTRAIN publications are available at <http://constrain-eu.org>.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820829.

HOW TO CITE

Myhre, G. and J. Quaas (2020). Improved characterization and understanding of the ERF concept. Knowledge Gains: Summary and Implication Report 1. The CONSTRAIN Project, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3715250

ABOUT CONSTRAIN

The 2015 Paris Agreement sets out a global action plan to avoid dangerous climate change by limiting global warming to well below 2°C, whilst pursuing efforts to limit warming to 1.5°C. However, predicting how the climate will change over the next 20-50 years, as well as defining the emissions pathways that will set and keep the world on track, requires a better understanding of how several human and natural factors will affect the climate in coming decades. These include how atmospheric aerosols affect the Earth’s radiation budget, and the roles of clouds and oceans in driving climate change.

The EU-funded CONSTRAIN project, a consortium of 14 European partners, is developing a better understanding of these variables, feeding them into climate models to reduce uncertainties, and creating improved climate projections for the next 20-50 years on regional as well as global scales.

In doing so, CONSTRAIN will take full advantage of existing knowledge from the Sixth Phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6) as well as other Horizon 2020 and European Research Council projects.

CONTACT CONSTRAIN

 <http://constrain-eu.org>

 @constrain-eu

For more information or to contact the authors, please email us:

 constrain@leeds.ac.uk